

Project acronym: CS3MESH4EOSC

Deliverable D3.5: Full definition and implementation of the protocol, platform and applications

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1 Introduction

This document describes the state of the protocol, APIs and applications in the ScienceMesh platform. It aims to provide a quick reference to the software repositories and documentation produced so far, as tangible results of the CS3MESH4EOSC Project.

At the time of writing, the project has not yet concluded, as it was extended by 6 months. However, the APIs and protocols, as well as the most basic applications, are at a very advanced development stage, and we do not expect major changes to them. Therefore, we hereby document them.

2 ScienceMesh Platform

The existing resources on the ScienceMesh platform are accessible through the web site <https://sciencemesh.io>

This website will also work as the entry point for the federated mesh once it is moved to production. It contains links to documentation, procedures and services used to join the mesh. Those are also described below.

Figure 1. Main ScienceMesh website

2.1 Central component

There are a few services which are run centrally, to support the mesh's federated architecture. These central components deal with the mesh federation metadata and with monitoring of meshed sites. They are described below.

2.1.1 Central Database

The central database is the source for Science Mesh federation metadata. This metadata typically contains the functional endpoints for API communication, technical contacts, security contacts and other important attributes needed to establish trust between sites in the infrastructure and then between their users. The base technology of the Central Database is GOCD (Grid Operations Configuration Management Database), developed by EGI (European Grid Infrastructure). The Central Database is operated by WWU (Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität Münster).

- GOCD: <https://gocdb.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de/gocdb/>

2.1.2 Mesh Directory

This Mesh Directory is responsible for routing users to their respective EFSS (Enterprise File Sync and Share) service in their own institutions, as part of the the process of establishing their identity. The Mesh Directory service generates a list of meshed sites based on the Science Mesh metadata delivered by the Central Database. User can pick from the list his/her EFSS system. Then the user is redirected to particular EFSS, where he/she can log in. After successful logging in the user's identity is revealed for the Science Mesh sharing procedures.

The service is currently run by CESNET, under the following URL: <https://sciencemesh.cesnet.cz/iop/meshdir/>

As the ScienceMesh hits production, a URL under the sciencemesh.io domain will be established.

Figure 2. Mesh Directory website

2.1.3 Site monitoring

The services responsible for monitoring are currently run by the WWU (Westfälische Wilhelms Universität Münster), at the following URLs:

- Grafana: <https://grafana.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de/>
- Prometheus: <https://prometheus.sciencemesh.uni-muenster.de/graph>

They will be moved to mesh-level domains for production operation of the infrastructure.

Figure 3. ScienceMesh dashboard

3 Protocols and APIs

The APIs and protocols used by the platform are documented and available for free under the following URLs:

- CS3APIs: <https://cs3org.github.io/cs3apis/>
- WebDAV: <https://www.rfc-editor.org/rfc/rfc4918.html>
- OCM: <https://cs3org.github.io/OCM-API/docs.html>

4 Software repositories

The software maintained by the project is available under the following GitHub open organisations:

- github.com/cs3org
 - Reva: <https://github.com/cs3org/rev>
 - CS3APIS: <https://github.com/cs3org/cs3apis>
 - WOPI Server: <https://github.com/cs3org/wopiserver>
- github.com/sciencemesh
 - Documentation: :

<https://github.com/sciencemesh/sciencemesh/tree/master/docs>

- Website: <https://github.com/sciencemesh/sciencemesh/>
- Deployment charts: <https://github.com/sciencemesh/charts>
- Jupyter integrator: <https://github.com/sciencemesh/filesystem-for-jupyter>
- MeshDirectory: <https://github.com/sciencemesh/meshdirectory-web>
- github.com/pondersource (this organisation is one of our outsourcing partners and while the code is currently hosted in their repositories it is expected that by the end of the project, they will be moved to github.com/sciencemesh).
- OC10 ScienceMesh app: <https://github.com/pondersource/oc-sciencemesh>
- Nextcloud ScienceMesh app: <https://github.com/pondersource/nc-sciencemesh>
- Nextcloud server patches: <https://github.com/pondersource/sciencemesh-nextcloud>

5 Conclusion

The ScienceMesh platform is now well established, and the software foundation has been gradually stabilized over the last two years. We do not expect major work ahead in terms of software development, or radical architecture changes, until the end of the CS3MESH4EOSC Project. The major challenge ahead is, then, to connect the platform with production services (Authentication, Storage, ...) in partner and external adopter sites.